

TABLE 2—3,5-DIMETHYL-4-(SUBSTITUTED SULFONAMIDO-BENZENE AZO, 4-SULFOPHENYL AZO AND 4-SULFONAPHTHYL AZO)PYRAZOLE

Sl. no.	X	R	M.p. °C
1	HOOCCH ₂ -	R _a	217
2	H ₃ C ₂ -	R _a	194
3	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	R _a	206
4	HOOCCH ₂ -	R _b	103
5	H ₃ C ₂ -	R _b	160
6	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	R _b	111
7	HOOCCH ₂ -	R _c	280
8	H ₃ C ₂ -	R _c	166
9	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	R _c	222
10	H ₃ C ₂ -	R _d	166
11	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	R _d	211
12	4-SO ₃ H-C ₆ H ₄ -	R _a	292
13	4-SO ₃ H-C ₁₀ H ₆ -	R _a	135
14	4-SO ₃ H-C ₆ H ₄ -	R _b	267
15	4-SO ₃ H-C ₁₀ H ₆ -	R _b	171
16	4-SO ₃ H-C ₆ H ₄ -	R _c	205
17	4-SO ₃ H-C ₁₀ H ₆ -	R _c	272
18	4-SO ₃ H-C ₁₀ H ₆ -	R _d	286

ture⁵. Azo dicarbonyl compounds were treated with the appropriate carbhydrazides using the procedure mentioned above, to obtain hydrazones (Table 1) and azo pyrazoles (Table 2), respectively.

Screening for antibacterial activity: The compounds in Table 2 have been evaluated for their antibacterial activity. The test organisms employed were *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The antibacterial activity of the compounds were tested by ditch plate technique⁶, using the concentration levels 2 mg and 3 mg per ml.

Compounds 1, 3 and 4 showed complete inhibition of *B. subtilis*. Compounds 12 and 16 showed complete inhibition of *S. aureus*. Compounds 12 and 16 showed complete inhibition of *S. typhi*, whereas compound 18 showed only partial inhibition. Compounds 14 and 16 showed complete inhibition of *P. aeruginosa*. The other compounds showed no activity on the organisms under study. None of the compounds studied showed any activity against *E. coli*. These results were identical for both the concentrations of the compounds studied.

(Ia)

(Ib)

(IIa)

(IIb)

Substituents R = R_a, R_b, R_c, R_d.

(R_d)

X =

HOOC-CH₂-

(Ia, IIa)

X =

(Ib, IIb)

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Reaction of Nitrosyl Chloride with Steroidal Olefins

SHAFIULLAH and M. RAFIUDDIN ANSARI

Steroid Research Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202 001

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NITROSYL chloride gas was used for chloronitrosation of steroidal alcohols¹ and oximes^{2,3}. The work of Tanabe *et al.*⁴ which dealt with the

action of nitrosyl chloride gas on some of the olefins prompted us to undertake an extension work in cholestane series.

This note reports the syntheses of 3 β ,5 α -dichloro-6 β -nitrocholestane (III) and 5 α -chloro-6 β -nitrocholestane (IV) when nitrosylchloride gas was passed in CCl₄ solution of 3 β -chlorocholest-5-ene (I) and cholest-5-ene (II), respectively at 0°.

Experimental

Nitrosyl chloride gas was prepared by the reported method⁵.

3 β -Chlorocholest-5-ene (I) (2 g) was dissolved in CCl₄ (100 ml) and cooled to 0°. Nitrosyl chloride gas was passed into the solution for 2 h. The solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure and the residue was dissolved in ether and washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and chromatographed over silica gel (40 g). Elution with petroleum ether-ether (40 : 1) gave compound 3 β ,5 α -dichloro-6 β -nitrocholestane (III) (1.5 g), crystallised from methanol, m.p. 111-113° (Found : C, 66.73 ; H, 9.22 ; N, 2.81. C₂₇H₄₅NO₂Cl₂ requires C, 66.80 ; H, 9.27 ; N, 2.88%) ; m/z 485/437 (3 : 1) and 439/441 (3 : 1) (M⁺-NO₂) ; ν_{max} 1555, 1360 (C-NO₂) and 735, 720 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl) ; δ (CDCl₃) 4.7 (dd, C₆- α H, J 6.5 Hz and 3.3 Hz, equatorial), 3.9 (mc, C₃- α H, $W_{1/2}$ 18Hz, axial, A/B ring junction trans), 2.6 (d, C₄-2H), 1.3 (s, C₁₀-CH₃), 0.78 (s, C₁₃-CH₃), 0.98 and 0.84 (other methyl protons).

Cholest-5-ene (II) (2 g) was dissolved in CCl₄ (100 ml) and cooled to 0°. Nitrosyl chloride gas was allowed to pass into the solution for 2 h. The solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure and the residue was dissolved in ether and washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and chromatographed over silica gel (40 g). Elution with petroleum ether-ether (20 : 1) provided 5 α -chloro-6 β -nitrocholestane (IV) (1.5 g), crystallised from methanol, gave positive Beilstein test, m.p. 91-93° (Found : C, 71.80 ; H, 10.14 ; N, 3.12. C₂₇H₄₅NO₂Cl requires C, 71.84 ; H, 10.20 ; N, 3.10%) ; m/z 451/453 (3 : 1) and 405/407 (3 : 1) (M⁺-NO₂) ; ν_{max} 1553, 1355 (C-NO₂) and 720 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl) ; δ (CDCl₃) 4.6 (dd, C₆- α H, J 6.4 Hz and 3.2 Hz, equatorial) 1.25 (s, C₁₀-CH₃), 0.72 (s, C₁₃-CH₃), 0.96 and 0.82 (other methyl protons).

Results and Discussion

The compound (III), m.p. 111-113° was analysed for C₂₇H₄₅NO₂Cl₂. The ir spectrum exhibited bands at 1555, 1360 cm⁻¹ (C-NO₂) and 735, 720 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl). In nmr spectrum signal of C₃-proton appeared at δ 3.9 ($W_{1/2}$, 18 Hz, axial, A/B ring junction trans)⁶. C₆ methine proton appeared at δ 4.7 (dd, J 6.5 Hz and 3.3 Hz, equatorial)⁶, therefore, disposition of C-NO₂ bond is axial. A clear doublet at δ 2.6 integrated for two protons is ascribable to C₄-2H. Mass spectrum corroborated the structure, which displayed weak molecular ion peaks at m/z 485/487 (3 : 1) and the diagnostic peaks at 439/441 (3 : 1) (M⁺-NO₂).

The compound IV, m.p. 91-93°, gave positive Beilstein test and analysed for C₂₇H₄₅NO₂Cl. The ir spectrum showed bands at 1553, 1355 (C-NO₂) and 720 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl). The nmr spectrum displayed a double doublet at δ 4.6 integrated for one proton (J 6.4 Hz and 3.2 Hz) ascribable to C₆- α H (equatorial). The structure was confirmed by mass spectrum which exhibited molecular ion peaks at m/z 451/453 (3 : 1) and 405/407 (3 : 1) (M⁺-NO₂).

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Hentriacontan-12-ol and Other Waxy Constituents of *Tamarix gallica* Linn.**

C. K. ANDHIWAL and KAMAL KISHORE*

Research Laboratory, Chemistry Department,
S. V. College, Aligarh-202 001

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TAMARIX gallica Linn. (Syn. *Tamarix troupil* Hole) commonly called *Jhau* belongs to family Tamaricaceae and is used in various ailments in Ayurvedic

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